

STAGES OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRY IN
KHOREZM REGION

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Annotation: *The article describes the prospects of industrial formation and development of Khorezm region.*

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Prior to the Russian invasion, handicrafts without factories and plant enterprises were well developed in the Khorezm region. At the end of the XIX and the beginning of the XX century in the khanate there were various private enterprises based on manual labor: coppersmithing, jewelry, blacksmithing, tannery, silk, dyeing, posing, ethics, pottery, sieves and cocoons (Matniyozov Page 81).

The Bolshaya Yaroslavskaya Manufaktura cotton and oil plant, built in 1889 in Urgench, is the first industrial enterprise in Khorezm. The plant is equipped with 5 gin, one hydraulic and a hand press, and gins 25,000 pounds of cotton a year. It is powered by electricity generated by a steam engine in the area of the plant. The plant's equipment is imported from the United States.

In 1904-1907, Poznansky and his company launched several large ginneries in the cities of Urgench, Mangit, Gurlan, Honka and Khiva (Matniyozov, p. 82).

By 1914, the number of ginneries in Khorezm reached 63. Of these, 13 were large and the rest were small businesses. 5 of them are located in Urgench, 2 in Gurlan, 3 in Tashkhovuz, one in Khiva, Mangit and Honqa. Local entrepreneurs have also invested in the sector, with five of the largest ginneries owned by local entrepreneurs.

In addition, other industrial enterprises have been built in the region. By the 1920s, in addition to ginneries, Khorezm had 11 brick factories, 8 alfalfa ginneries, 4 leather factories, and 4 oil and soap factories.

The capacity of the existing plants was not very large. In the 1990s, all the factories in the khanate ginned only 85,000 pounds of cotton. The first 40 kW power plant in Khorezm was built in 1912 in Khiva.

During the Khorezm revolution and the ensuing civil war, large factory and plant owners fled their property, some enterprises were destroyed, many were shut down due to a lack of raw materials and a lack of specialists.

After the October coup, most of the enterprises in Khorezm were closed during the civil war. No new industrial enterprises have been built due to lack of funds, construction materials and specialists. In 1923, a much larger power plant was commissioned in Khiva. In

1924, 575,000 soums were given to the Khorezm government for the restoration and repair of cotton gins and oil mills. In 1925, ginneries were opened in Khiva and Hazarasp. In 1928-1929, a new cotton gin was built in Urgench, and in 1932, a clover seed ginning plant was built. In general, during this period, 24 large industrial enterprises were built and put into operation in Khorezm. As a result of the construction of 12 industrial enterprises in the region in 1928, by 1940 their number had risen to 50,

In the regional energy sector, electricity has been generated during these years using internal combustion engines. In 1913, the capacity of the only power station in Khiva was barely enough to light the khan's palace, but by 1940, with the help of existing power plants and electric motors in the country, 2.3 million. kWh of electricity generated. However, in the years before World War II, there were almost no enterprises belonging to heavy industry, and the products in the industry were produced mainly in small enterprises, in handicraft cooperatives belonging to local industry. In 1926, there were 26 such artels in Khorezm district, which employed more than 2,000 workers.

Another reason for the backwardness of the region's industrial production is that it was not connected with the republic and other regions of the former Soviet Union by rail until the 1950s. This led to the failure of a number of industrial projects planned to be relocated during the Second World War. In particular, the construction of the Shovot HPP in 1944, a spinning and weaving factory in Urgench, and a brewery were not built. During this period, the Khiva Oil Refinery (1944) was launched. Out of the region, the cargo was sent from the Cholish pier via the Amudarya. The cargo was transported from Urgench to Cholish by a narrow-gauge railway.

The post-war years in Khorezm are characterized by rapid growth of all sectors of the economy, including transport, industry and energy. One of the factors driving this growth was the construction and commissioning of the Chorjoi-Urgench-Kungrad railway in 1953. Along with the construction of the railway, gasification has played an important role in the growth of the regional economy and improving the living standards of the population. In 1966, the construction of the Bukhara-Urals and Central Asia-Central Asia main gas pipeline through the region led to a certain degree of natural gas supply to utilities, industry and agriculture.

The installation of a 250,000 kW power train in Urgench in 1958, the commissioning of the first stage of the Takhiatash GRES in 1960 and the construction of the Takhiatash-Urgench power transmission line in 1963 made a significant change in the economic and social life of the region. In particular, during 1966-1970, large industrial enterprises in the region, including: silicate, reinforced concrete, building materials, large-panel housing, bread, factories, Khiva sewing factory, Shovot, Yangiarik, Yangibazar ginneries, tire repair plant, Jumurtov stone crushing - A sorting plant and a number of local industrial complexes have been built and put into operation. As a result, by 1970, the number of large industrial enterprises in the region reached 70. The volume of industrial gross domestic product increased by 371% compared to 1940.

In the early 1970s, the second stage of the 154-kilometer-long Takhiatash-Urgench transmission line was put into operation, and Khorezm was connected to the republican

power system via the 144-kilometer-long Duldul-Urgench high-voltage power line. This event led to the further development of the region's industry. Small energy-intensive electrical installations have been shut down in the region.

Between 1971-1975 and 1976-1980, Khorezm was a pioneer in the development of industry and energy. During this period, about 15 large industrial enterprises were built and put into operation, including the Urgench silk-spinning factory, oil extraction and excavator repair plant, Khiva carpet factory. It was the construction of the Tuyamoyin hydraulic complex and hydroelectric power station that ushered in a new era in regional energy. After the construction of the Tuyamoyin HPP, the use of electricity in the lower Amudarya zone has doubled. As a result, between 1970 and 1988, the region's industrial output increased by 252 percent or 2.52 times

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